

Cyber defense framework for 5G/6G using a Network Digital Twin

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Abstract—With the rapid evolution of 5G and emerging 6G networks, ensuring security against DDoS threats remains a pressing challenge, particularly due to expanded attack surfaces across the edge–cloud continuum and heterogeneous edge devices. Traditional security mechanisms struggle to provide proactive, scalable, and low-risk detection and classification solutions in such highly dynamic environments. This paper proposes a Network Digital Twin (NDT)–driven framework for DDoS detection, analysis, and classification in 5G/6G networks, leveraging a synchronized digital twin for safe attack emulation and AI/ML-based anomaly detection. We implement and validate the framework on a real 5G testbed combined with an operational NDT platform, demonstrating that the NDT accurately reproduces network behavior under both normal and attack conditions and validating its efficacy for DT-driven, adaptive security in next-generation mobile systems.

Index Terms—5G, 6G Networks, Network Digital Twin, NDT, Cybersecurity, DDOS attack, Network Traffic Analysis, Attack Emulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition towards 6G networks introduces unprecedented levels of flexibility, programmability, and intelligence, but also significantly expands the cyber-attack surface [1], [2]. Cloud-native network functions, service-based architectures, network slicing, and Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) deployments collectively create fertile ground for Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, which can affect both data-plane and control-plane services and cause significant harm including service disruptions, revenue loss, and increased security expenditure [3].

State-of-the-art DDoS detection in mobile networks increasingly relies on AI/ML-driven analytics [4], [5], shifting from signature-based systems toward learning-based traffic classification. In 5G/6G environments these approaches are embedded within programmable controllers or (Network Data Analytics Function) NWDAF-assisted pipelines, enabling near–real-time detection [6].

While such techniques significantly improve detection accuracy and adaptability compared to legacy methods, current state-of-the-art solutions are predominantly evaluated in controlled or offline settings and remain tightly coupled to the availability and quality of training data [7]. Recent studies highlight that many (Machine Learning) ML-driven DDoS solutions rely on outdated, unrealistic or non-representative synthetic, or highly imbalanced datasets, which fail to reflect

the dynamics of cloud-native network functions, service-based architectures, and slice-aware traffic patterns, thereby limiting model generalization and robustness [4], [7]. This dataset limitation is exacerbated by the fact that validating detection and mitigation mechanisms directly on production networks is inherently risky, as reactive countermeasures deployed on live infrastructures may trigger service disruption, inaccurate policy enforcement, or cascading failures across tightly coupled control and data plane components [8]. Consequently, despite extensive research efforts, existing DDoS mitigation strategies remain largely reactive, operating after attack manifestation and under constrained validation conditions [9].

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND PAPER CONTRIBUTIONS

To address these challenges, the NDT paradigm has emerged as a promising enabler for safe, controllable, and repeatable generation of realistic network datasets [10]. In [11], we presented an NDT framework tailored for 5G/6G networks, demonstrating accurate network topology modeling and seamless synchronization with real-world operations.

However, the potential of NDTs for security-focused, closed-loop defense remains largely underexplored. By maintaining a continuously synchronized virtual replica of the physical network, an NDT allows safe attack emulation, predictive analysis, and validation of mitigation strategies without impacting live services.

This paper presents an NDT-driven DDoS detection and classification framework for 5G/6G networks, building on the architecture of [11]. Two representative DDoS vectors are instantiated within the NDT: TCP SYN flood and GTP-U flood, capturing fine-grained traffic and performance characteristics under both normal and adversarial conditions for precise attack labelling.

The proposed AI/ML classifier trains exclusively on high-fidelity NDT-generated datasets, which—unlike conventional synthetic data—maintain continuous bidirectional synchronization with the physical network, ensuring datasets accurately capture real 5G/6G operational characteristics.

The trained model is then deployed for inference on a physical Amarisoft 5G testbed, achieving strong detection and classification performance despite training solely on synthetic NDT data, validating the NDT-driven workflow for bridging emulated and real 5G/6G environments.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section III presents the NDT framework; Section IV describes the experimental setup and attack models; Section V presents the results; and Section VI concludes the paper.

III. NDT FRAMEWORK DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

An NDT is defined as a virtual representation of a physical network, enabling enhanced understanding, control, and optimization of network operations [12]. Building upon this definition, an NDT modelling approach for 5G networks, as is presented in [11], is comprised of three main components as shown in Figure 1 namely: i) the NDT Data Repository, responsible for collecting, organizing, and storing telemetry data from the Physical Network (PN) and NDT; ii) the NDT Engine, which maps the PN topology to its virtual NDT counterpart replica according to the testing scenario and iii) the NDT Management, which oversees orchestration, monitoring, and evaluation of NDT operations.

The implementation of the proposed NDT framework follows a modular and scalable architecture that integrates open-source tools to support 5G/6G network emulation, monitoring, and AI/ML-based security analysis. The framework components are designed to operate cohesively, enabling efficient data generation, model training, simulation, and evaluation in a controlled environment

Fig. 1: Network Digital Twin framework for native-AI support in a 5G/6G system.

A. Data Repository

The Data Repository serves as a centralized store for real-time and historical network data, encompassing user traffic, attack patterns, and telemetry for AI/ML model training and evaluation. Traffic data is captured from various network interfaces and stored directly in the repository. For network telemetry, Prometheus [13] is employed as the metrics collection and retrieval layer — it periodically scrapes metrics from NDT Engine components and selected Physical Network elements, storing them in its built-in time-series database.

This makes Prometheus well-suited for handling both real-time monitoring and historical data queries at scale. These capabilities support structured dataset generation for AI/ML-based detection and classification tasks.

B. NDT Engine

The NDT Engine models the Physical Network to its virtual counterpart via the Network Modeling Service. It supports multiple parallel instances (NDT 1, NDT 2, ..., NDT n) representing different network layers or segments, enabling scalable testing of complex models. The AI/ML analytics engine provides virtual validation of models before real-world deployment.

The NDT Engine comprises software components capable of emulating the functionalities of a 5G Core System, providing capabilities for configuration of all available core 5G Network Functions (i.e. Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), User Plane Function (UPF), etc.). In our implementation, the 5GC is implemented via Open5GS [14]. The NDT Engine also allows for Radio Access Network (RAN) and UE simulation/emulation, allowing for complete 5G implementation in the NDT. In our implementation, the UERANSIM 5G UE gateway and RAN (gNodeB) simulator [15] is used. These components enable comprehensive emulation of the 5G network stack, from RAN to core, while supporting controlled reproduction of normal and adversarial traffic. Specifically for the current work, a digital replica of a 5G Mobile network is built, and a mobile network traffic mix is generated including benign traffic from normal users and DDOS attacks from malicious users. The generated data are ingested into the considered AI/ML model, whose implementation is presented in the next section. These data serve as the primary source for training and inference, enabling continuous learning and validation of the models. This approach allows for safe experimentation and systematic evaluation of DDoS detection and classification techniques without impacting the live 5G network.

C. NDT Management

The NDT Management component orchestrates diverse network topologies via the NG.116 Generic Network Slice Template [16], while also supporting end-to-end services that extend beyond basic connectivity. This capability enhances the detail and complexity of possible network topologies and instances that may be simulated by the NDT. In our implementation, the KATANA Slice Manager [17] synchronizes workflows across the NDT Engine and Data Repository, handling NDT instance lifecycle and supporting repeatable experimentation for controlled attack execution and AI/ML evaluation.

The NDT Visualization Service delivers graphical insights via Grafana [18], offering interactive dashboards for real-time monitoring of network behavior, traffic characteristics, and model performance throughout the NDT lifecycle.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP DESCRIPTION

A. Testbed Deployment

The testbed couples a real 5G mobile network with its NDT. The physical network uses the Amarisoft 5G Call Box [19] for both RAN and core functionality. The scenario includes six UEs in a single cell: four benign UEs generating TCP traffic mixes (video streaming and application flows) at a QoS SLA of 10 Mbps each, and two adversarial UEs that initiate DDoS attacks upon activation.

The two malicious endpoints are Raspberry Pi platforms with Waveshare SIM8200EA-M2 5G HAT modules, generating SYN floods and GTP-U floods to stress both the access and core network. All traffic is captured in real-time via Wireshark, producing PCAP files fed directly into the NDT-hosted deep learning models.

The setup is represented in the NDT, which is configured to replicate the same network topology, configuration, and operational behavior as the physical network. Consequently, the exact same experimental setup is reused within the NDT, including identical RAN and core-network components, traffic profiles, and attack scenarios. This one-to-one correspondence ensures that the traffic observed in the digital twin represents the traffic dynamics of the real network, enabling the AI/ML detection and classification models to be trained and evaluated under equivalent conditions. As a result, model validation can be performed in the NDT without impacting live services, while maintaining high fidelity between physical deployment and its digital counterpart.

B. Attack Models

Two representative volumetric and protocol-aware DDoS attacks targeting different 5G core layers are considered. Each is instantiated with controlled parameters—packet size, rate, and target interface—as shown in TABLE I, ensuring repeatability in both the physical network and its NDT counterpart.

1) *SYN Flood*: The SYN flood generates high-rate TCP SYN packets targeting the host running the Open5GS user-plane network functions (UPF). The attack exhausts TCP connection backlogs by creating incomplete three-way handshakes, leading to increased CPU utilization and blocking legitimate signaling connections [20].

2) *GTP-U Flood*: The GTP-U flood targets the UPF N3 interface with crafted GTP-U packets using invalid Tunnel Endpoint Identifiers (TEIDs). The UPF processes each packet, performs failed tunnel lookups, and generates Error Indication responses (message type 56). This stresses GTP-U parsing, tunnel tables, and data packets processing. Indicators include GTP-U Error messages and abnormal UPF interface rx/tx counters [21].

TABLE I: DDoS Attack Parameters

Attack	Packet Size	Rate	Target
SYN	~70 bytes	5000 pps	L4 (TCP)
GTP-U	~1235 bytes	5000 pps	UPF N3

C. AI/ML Analysis for Detection & Classification

The raw PCAP dataset is parsed to extract per-packet information and compute per-second, per-source-IP aggregated statistics. Features (TABLE II) include packet/byte count rates, packet-size statistics, inter-arrival time metrics, and uplink/downlink bitrates. Attack instances are labelled using known attacker IPs, creating three classes: benign, SYN flood, and GTP-U flood.

TABLE II: Packet and Flow-Level AI/ML Algorithm Features

Feature	Description
packet_count	Packets per second from source IP
byte_count	Total bytes per second
avg_packet_size	Mean packet size (bytes)
min_packet_size	Smallest packet size
max_packet_size	Largest packet size
packet_size_variance	Population variance of packet sizes
inter_arrival_time_mean	Average time between packets (sec)
inter_arrival_time_variance	Variance of inter-arrival times
packet_rate_pps	Packets per second rate (pps)
ul_bitrate	Uplink bitrate (ul) (bps)
dl_bitrate	Downlink bitrate (dl) (bps)

These features capture discriminative rate, volume, and timing signatures of DDoS activity. Packet/byte rates reflect traffic surges typical of SYN floods; packet-size statistics distinguish attack modalities (small SYN probes vs. larger GTP-U payloads); inter-arrival time statistics characterize burstiness and separate high-rate attack streams from benign flows.

The proposed method employs a supervised multi-class Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) [22] classifier. Features are standardized via an 80-20 stratified split and scaled with StandardScaler [23] fitted on training data, then reshaped to $[N, 1, F]$ for LSTM input. The model has a two-layer LSTM (hidden size 64, dropout 0.2 between layers), that processes each sample as a one-time step. It extracts the final hidden state, applies dropout, then uses a fully connected layer to output logits for three classes: benign (0), SYN flood (1) and GTP-U flood (2).

Training uses Cross Entropy Loss [24], Adam optimizer [25] (lr=0.001, weight decay 1e-4), batch size 64, gradient clipping (max norm 1.0), for 30 epochs. Evaluation produces a classification report with per-class precision, recall, and F1-scores. The internal state of the LSTM memory cell is computed using the following equations:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i x_t + U_i h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (1a)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f x_t + U_f h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (1b)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o x_t + U_o h_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (1c)$$

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{c}_t \quad (1d)$$

$$\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_c x_t + U_c h_{t-1} + b_c) \quad (1e)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \quad (1f)$$

Fig. 2: Per-UE traffic flows in both Physical Network and NDT testbeds under SYN Flood and GTP-U Flood DDoS attacks.

Here i_t, f_t, o_t are the input, forget, and output gates; c_t the cell state; x_t the input at step t ; h_{t-1} the previous hidden state; W, U, b are trainable parameters; \odot denotes element-wise product; and $\sigma(\cdot)$ the sigmoid function.

To address class imbalance—benign samples far outnumber attack samples—we apply Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) [26] to synthesize realistic minority-class examples during training.

V. RESULTS ANALYSIS

A. AI/ML Analysis for Detection & Classification

Our testing scenario evaluates the NDT’s accuracy and reliability by comparing its behavior against the Physical Network under identical conditions. Benign UEs start exchanging traffic from time zero; malicious UEs launch attacks at specific time epochs. The first row in Figure 2 presents the per-UE traffic flows observed in the Physical Network testbed under the SYN Flood (Fig. 2a) and GTP-U Flood (Fig. 2b) attacks. For the SYN attack, Malicious UE 1 (red line) attacks from 70–150s and Malicious UE 2 (yellow line) from 100–130s. For the GTP-U attack, Malicious UE 1 attacks from 30–80s and Malicious UE 2 from 45–90s. The corresponding NDT flows are shown in the second row of Figure 2 (Figs. 2c, 2d), exhibiting consistent behavior. In both environments, benign UEs operate at 10Mbps and suffer throughput degradation during the attack, especially in the case of when the two malicious UEs attack together, recovering fully upon its termination. It

must be discussed that per-UE flows are not exactly replicated between environments due to the inherently stochastic nature of UE packet-sending decisions.

To quantify NDT fidelity, we aggregate benign-UE traffic and compute the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distance [27]—a similarity metric robust to timing shifts—between the Physical Network and NDT time series. As shown in Figures 3a and 3b, aggregated throughput traces are very close for both attack types. The DTW distance (Figs. 3c, 3d) remains consistently low, with a mean of 14.2 for SYN and 9.6 for GTP-U.

These results confirm that the NDT closely replicates the traffic patterns, QoS performance, and attack scenarios of the physical network, providing a controlled and scalable environment for AI/ML model training and offline optimization before Physical Network deployment.

As seen in Table III, the LSTM classifier achieved 99% accuracy across the three-class task. Benign traffic yielded near-perfect F1 (0.99), and attack classes (SYN, GTP-U) achieved robust F1-scores of 0.86 and 0.92 despite class imbalance. The macro-average F1 of 0.93 confirms balanced discrimination across all classes, validating that per-second statistical features effectively capture distinct signatures for both benign 5G traffic patterns and protocol-specific flood attacks.

(a) SYN Flood – Aggregated Throughput

(b) GTP-U Flood – Aggregated Throughput

(c) SYN Flood – Dynamic Time Warping (DTW)

(d) GTP-U Flood – Dynamic Time Warping (DTW)

Fig. 3: Aggregated benign-UE throughput (Physical vs. NDT) and DTW distance over time for SYN Flood and GTP-U Flood attacks.

TABLE III: Cross-Validation 3-fold Classification report

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign (0)	0.99	1.00	1.00	6481
SYN (1)	0.87	0.84	0.86	140
GTPU (2)	1.00	0.86	0.92	136
accuracy			0.99	6757
macro avg.	0.96	0.90	0.93	6757
weighted avg.	0.99	0.99	0.99	6757

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an NDT-based framework for detecting and classifying DDoS attacks in 5G networks. Combining a real 5G network with its NDT enables safe emulation of normal and malicious traffic, providing high-fidelity datasets for AI/ML training without impacting live operations. The NDT accurately reproduced network behavior under SYN and GTP-U flood attacks, and the proposed LSTM classifier achieved F1-scores above 0.90 for all attack types. Studies for UDP and ICMP-based DDoS attacks yielded similar results but are omitted here due to space constraints.

Future work will focus on deeper integration of the NDT with AI-native network functions to support closed-loop security workflows, enabling continuous validation and optimization of detection models before live deployment.

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